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Open Science & Evidence-Informed Decision Making

LESSONS LEARNED

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INTRODUCTION

The 'Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making' (EIDM) Learning Path is a targeted Train-the-Trainer Initiative, developed under the Skills4EOSC project, specifically designed for policymakers, civil servants, knowledge brokers and all stakeholders interested in Open Science and decision making. The learning path addresses the pressing need to equip these professional profiles with the knowledge, skills, and competences to engage with and apply Open Science principles in policy development and evidence-informed decision making. The programme aimed to improve policy effectiveness, transparency and trust by equipping participants with practical skills and knowledge.

This training pathway is not a general-purpose curriculum but one tailored to the distinctive needs and roles of policy sector professionals. Recognising that little existing training material fully addressed these profiles, the development process combined a landscaping analysis of relevant initiatives with the creation of original, purpose-built content. The goal was to ensure that the training program responds directly to the real-world responsibilities, constraints, and opportunities faced by decision-makers and intermediaries in public administrations.

Methodology

The training was designed using the FAIR-by-design methodology and anchored in the Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVS) framework developed in Skills4EOSC. This helped to identify learning needs and formulate key messages and learning outcomes aligned with the target professional profiles and their required competences.

The Skills4EOSC FAIR-by-design methodology provides a comprehensive framework for the development of learning materials, offering clear, structured guidance on how to create FAIR training resources whilst being flexible with the choice of tools, platforms and content formats. The methodology aims to empower the popular backward instructional design process with additional activities related to the creation of FAIR learning materials from both, the perspective of trainers aiming for future reuse, and the trainees requiring easy access and usability.

Composition

Building on this tailored approach, the Train-the-Trainer curriculum was organised into a series of modules, each targeting specific learning outcomes and designed to gradually develop participants' competences. This systematic structure ensured that the training is not only theoretically sound but also practically applicable, directly supporting the professional responsibilities of policymakers, civil servants, and knowledge brokers. The training program was implemented through a blended learning approach, combining self-paced and live online sessions to provide flexibility while maintaining interactive elements. To support this delivery model, several tools and platforms were used both for developing the content and for engaging participants during the sessions.

In total, 20 modules with 45 lectures were developed, split into seven different courses:

- EIDM Train-the-Trainer Course 1: "Open Science is the new norm"
- EIDM Train-the-Trainer Course 2: "Ethical, Legal and Societal Implications (ELSI) and Data Governance"
- EIDM Train-the-Trainer Course 3: "Introduction to Evidence-informed Decision Making"
- EIDM Train-the-Trainer Course 4: "Open Science Stakeholders and Collaboration Strategies"
- EIDM Train-the-Trainer Course 5: "Empowering the Future of Research with Open Science"
- EIDM Train-the-Trainer Course 6: "Open Science Policies support Open Science Practices"
- EIDM Train-the-Trainer Course 7: "Implementing Open Science Policies"

For each of the courses, a different Specialist certification (badge) was provided, with an additional one for the Instructors that completed the full series of courses.

Impact

The EIDM Train-the-trainer learning path attracted wide international participation from universities, research institutes, government bodies, and cultural organizations, demonstrating its broad reach and cross-sectoral relevance during two rounds of training. The program strengthened participants' skills in applying Open Science principles and evidence-informed decision making, fostering a dynamic ecosystem of stakeholders capable of supporting the implementation of Open Science policies and practices.

To evaluate the effectiveness and relevance of the EIDM training, participant feedback was collected after each of the seven courses and at the end of the learning path, for each round of training. Evaluation forms captured both quantitative and qualitative responses on various aspects, including content clarity, relevance, usability, engagement and overall satisfaction.

Additional resources and events

Finally, additional resources and relevant events supported the training learning path. The additional resources include booklets and materials developed in the other tasks of the work package, which were used within the courses as supplementary readings to deepen participants' understanding on different topics.

For more details, you can visit the full report, D3.2 Evidence-based policy and Public Administration training final report, available in Zenodo¹. This document summarises the lessons learned from all the processes performed for the development, delivery and feedback on the EIDM Learning path.

Lessons Learned, Best Practices and Next Steps

The development and delivery of the training programme on Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making (EIDM) offered valuable insights related both to the content needs and the practical challenges of building capacity in policy making. The next section summarises some key lessons learned through the whole design and delivery process, provides recommendations for future relevant activities and highlights some possible next steps to build on in future activities.

¹ Evangelinou, B. (2025). D3.2 Evidence-based policy and Public Administration training final report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16992250>

LESSONS LEARNED

Designing for Relevance and Reusability

A structured methodology, including the Minimum Viable Skillset Framework, the FAIR-by-design Methodology, and the Quality Assurance Framework, with alignment with ethical, legal and social aspects (ELSI), proved essential in the design and delivery of the training material, ensuring quality, coherence, and adaptability. However, one of the challenges faced during the development of the training content was the lack of existing training resources tailored to the specific profiles of the target audience of the course. This required the team to design a curriculum in a way to address these gaps in a meaningful and scalable way.

Given the diverse backgrounds and geographical contexts of the participants, the content had to be both pedagogically relevant and practically applicable across multiple audiences. The modular and clear design of the learning path and the organisation of the vast amount of different modules into individual but interconnected courses facilitated reuse and adaptation of the content, as well as integration into other training initiatives, both within but also beyond the project activities.

Balancing Flexibility and Engagement

An important lesson from the training experience was the challenge to maintain the participants engagement in a fully flexible, non-mandatory learning environment. The combination of the self-paced format with shorter live sessions enabled participants to manage their learning according to their own schedules, but in parallel create a sense of community and interaction. This approach was particularly effective given the diverse professional responsibilities and time constraints of participants from different countries, including those beyond Europe. However, the voluntary nature of the course revealed a spectrum of engagement: some participants joined simply to access specific content, while others were really engaged and actively participated in all the course activities, motivated by the opportunity to earn a formal certification. This experience emphasised the need to support the learners autonomy, while offering optional motivation to help participants remain engaged, without applying pressure or make participation obligatory. Finally, the blended model of self-paced content and live sessions proved to be a very valuable element, as it supported different learning preferences and provided opportunities for clarification, deeper discussions, real-time engagement, interaction and networking, all while preserving the flexibility of the overall course design.

Streamlining Assessment Practices

The shift from manually graded individual assignments to structured, auto-corrected quizzes in the second round of trainings really improved sustainability, streamlined the assessment process for the trainers and supported self-assessed learning. Introducing limited attempts in a certain timeframe and randomised questions from a larger question bank also helped maintain integrity and encouraged more thoughtful engagement with the material, reducing the likelihood of rote memorisation. The participants' very positive feedback on the value of the quizzes and how they enabled them to meaningfully assess their understanding, highlights the importance of well-crafted assessments in supporting learning and reflection in a self-paced environment. Although the more complex activities used as individual assessments in the first round were no longer mandatory in the second round of trainings, they remained an important resource. These exercises, presented as group activities during the live sessions, proved especially valuable for the participants, as they offered interactivity and community building between them, as well as ready-to-use, tested material that could be easily adapted and reused in future trainings.

Strengthening Community and Continuity

The course played an important role in fostering a strong sense of community, by encouraging collaboration, interactivity, shared learning and networking. Group activities, live discussions, shared learning experiences promoted peer engagement and the exchange of ideas and perspectives, something that was really valuable for the participants to connect across different countries and disciplines. As a Train-the-Trainer programme, the course brought together future trainers from many countries, who not only benefited from the learning experience, but also already began forming potential networks that could support their future training activities. These connections and experiences laid the foundation for ongoing collaboration, long-term networking and knowledge sharing, beyond the scope of the course and the project itself.

Promoting Reuse and Adaptation

A key achievement of the training course is the demonstrated versatility and adaptability of its materials. The content developed within this learning path was actively reused and adapted in multiple ways across different contexts. Project partners incorporated material into other training courses and activities, both within and beyond the scope of the project. Most notably, the national pilot trainings, that were organised by each participating country as a follow-up to the main Train-the-Trainers programme, served as an important testbed for reuse, within different audience needs and local settings. Moreover, course alumni also played a role in promoting reuse. Several participants informed us about including and adapting material in trainings in their own institutions and local events.

All the above initiatives highlight the multiplier effect of the course and its contribution to the long-term capacity building efforts in Open Science and evidence-informed decision making. This impact was made possible thanks to the broad applicability and accessibility of the course materials, provided in multiple types and formats, including slide decks, video lectures, instructors notes, case studies, additional reading materials, and practical activities. Their modular and adaptable nature supported the participants to reuse, translate and embed them into various educational and professional settings. This flexibility not only enhanced the content usefulness for future trainers, but also supported the need not to “reinvent the wheel” and allow for ongoing reuse of already tested, high-quality resources.

RECOMMENDATIONS AND BEST PRACTICES

Drawing from the training experience within the entire lifecycle of the project, below you can find some recommendations and best practices that could potentially guide similar capacity building efforts:

- 1. Use a modular course design:** Standalone modules that can be reused, adapted or delivered independently can support scalability, flexibility and customisation in different contexts.
- 2. Include practical examples:** Incorporate real-world cases and applied scenarios throughout the training to help participants connect abstract concepts with tangible practices. This approach enhances understanding, supports adaptation and prepares participants to apply knowledge in their own professional environments.
- 3. Provide multi-format material:** Offer materials in accessible formats (video lectures, editable slides, instructors notes, open documents, etc) to enable easy understanding and reuse. Instructors notes with narrative are really valuable for participants, in order to follow the content easily but also prepare for future trainings. Video lectures also enhance engagement in a self-paced environment.
- 4. Combine multiple types of learning experiences and engagement:** A self-paced content is always preferable for busy professionals in different countries, but the possibility to attend a live session that would allow for clarifications, interactivity, collaboration and community building is really important and recognised by the participants, without compromising flexibility.
- 5. Provide additional resources for interested learners:** Offer supplementary materials, such as readings, case studies, and toolkits to support deeper understanding and exploration beyond the course content. This helps participants personalise their learning experience and engage more with certain topics of interest.
- 6. Include well-crafted assessment methods:** Design assessments that are meaningful, manageable and aligned with the learning objectives of the course to encourage reflection and knowledge retention. Use a variety of assessment methods depending on the structure of the course, to balance the learners engagement, practical use and scalability.
- 7. Provide motivation incentives:** Offer recognition opportunities, such as certificates, badges, or other rewarding mechanisms, to motivate participants and encourage deeper engagement.
- 8. Encourage Feedback:** Actively seek for participants' feedback at multiple stages in the development and delivery stages of the training, to understand the audience needs, improve course design and enhance the learning experience.
- 9. Create a valuable user experience:** Design the course environment to be user-friendly, intuitive and accessible. Incorporate a variety of interactive elements, ensure navigation is straightforward, materials are clear and easy to find and the overall experience encourages continuous participation and engagement.

NEXT STEPS/SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE ACTIVITIES

The following ideas outline some potential steps forward for building on the achievements of the project. While these activities fall beyond the scope of the project and the current timeline, they represent valuable opportunities for further growth and impact. These suggestions aim to inspire future initiatives, such as through the Competence Centre network activities but also other potential collaborations, that can further strengthen and expand the reach of the project's outcomes.

Some of them include:

- 1. Create a trainer Support Network – Community of Practice** to foster a collaborative environment between different countries and Competence Centres, where trainers can share experiences, resources and best practices.
- 2. Refine and Update Course Content** regularly, ensuring that the materials remain up-to-date, include latest developments in the Open Science landscape and continue to meet the evolving needs of the learners.
- 3. Translate Course Materials in different languages** to increase accessibility and inclusivity, and thus allow a broader and more diverse audience to benefit from the training resources worldwide.
- 4. Support future training events** using the experience and material from the courses and delivery methods, facilitating a wider dissemination of knowledge and skills.
- 5. Develop microlearning units** as shorter, focused modules using course material for emerging topics or topics of wider interest, to further enhance the learners engagement and skills.
- 6. Create toolkits and additional readings** for certain topics of interest and provide learners with more practical resources and deeper insights, in different disciplines and contexts.
- 7. Expand content in settings** beyond Europe to foster inclusivity, international collaboration and global impact.

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